

The Influence of Product Quality, Service Quality, and Price Towards Customer Purchase Decision at Starbucks Coffee in Diponegoro Medan

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ABSTRACT

The effect of service quality has a significant positive effect on Starbucks Coffee customer purchase decision at Diponegoro Medan, meaning that the better the service, the higher the level of satisfaction obtained by consumers. This is reasonable because consumers always see the most important in terms of service quality. The effect of product quality has a significant positive effect on Starbucks Coffee customer purchase decision in Diponegoro, Medan meaning that the better the product quality, the higher the level of satisfaction created and obtained by consumers. This is reasonable because consumers feel their desires are fulfilled in product quality. The effect of price has a positive but not significant effect on Starbucks Coffee customer purchase decision in Diponegoro, Medan meaning that consumers are indeed satisfied with the quality of service and product quality created, but consumers do not see much from the Starbucks price perspective. Consumers see more in terms of services and products provided

INTRODUCTION

In this millennial era, business development is happening rapidly. The growth of various businesses occurs everywhere. Every businessman is forced by strong competition to use all of their resources in order to compete with already established companies in their industry, which makes it increasingly necessary for firms to move more quickly to draw in customers.

The development of the culinary business are currently influenced by various factors such as demographics, increasing economic levels, and people's lifestyles. It is evidenced by the growing number of culinary businesses with a variety of concepts, such as family restaurants, street stalls, bistros, and cafes. People nowadays are more likely to have busy life and high mobility. In today's society, people spend more of their time away from home. For practical and convenient reasons, they tend to visit restaurants more frequently to gather with family, friends, clients, or simply to relax in the midst of their hectic lives.

The Indonesian population is changing, favoring the activity of drinking coffee at coffee shops more and more. Coffee is now more than simply a drowsiness reliever; it is a part of a culture where going to coffee shops is highly common. Coffee shops are typically utilized, according to Yana (2018), as a location for people to gather and relax with friends or family on weekends or just to relieve exhaustion from daily activities. Many students use the existence of this coffee shop as an additional location to finish work or schoolwork.

Starbucks is one of the coffee shops that is currently expanding quickly. The headquarters of the American coffee corporation Starbucks Corporation are in Seattle, Washington. PT. Mitra Adiperkasa Tbk runs the Starbucks coffee franchise in Indonesia. With more than 150 locations, Starbucks is already present in 11 cities around Indonesia (Nurhasanah & Dewi, 2019). Starbucks sells coffee, tea, and complementary sweets on its menu.

Starbucks Diponegoro is one of the Starbucks branches in the city of Medan. Established on September, 2017, which is located on Jl Diponegoro No. 5 Medan, SU 20519. Starbucks Diponegoro offers Coffee, Tea, Patisserie and Merchandise. Like many coffee shops, Starbucks Diponegoro is suitable as a hangout place for family, friends, of all ages. The cafe concept of Starbucks Diponegoro is an indoor coffee shops, but for the convenience of other visitors, Starbucks Diponegoro also provides an outdoor room with facilities such as air conditioning and smoking friendly.

Starbucks continually holds the top spot and is the brand that customers think of when thinking about coffee shops in Indonesia. The appropriate strategy must be chosen by companies in order for them to succeed and outperform the competition and achieve their objectives. The right brand image of the product is very important to consumers in order to satisfy their current needs. This is one of the factors that businesses must take into account in order to satisfy customer expectations.

In addition to brand image, brand awareness also influences the buyer's decision in choosing a product. Marketing and advertising are mostly determined by brand awareness strategy. However, customers must first be aware of a product's existence for it to become a brand. Consumers' inability to

recall a product's name alone is a sign that the existing marketing approach is unsuccessful. This understanding is demonstrated by consumers' memory and recognition of a brand's traits and their ability to identify those traits with a particular category.

Based on the background of the problem, the title of this research is "The Influence of Product Quality, Service Quality, Price towards Customer Purchase Decision at Starbucks Coffee in Diponegoro, Medan".

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Hospitality Management

Hospitality management is a career path commonly associated with the hotel, resort, and lodging industries. Many aspects of the guest experience are created and managed by professionals in the field. They are also often in charge of teams that include front desk staff, housekeeping and sales. Based on Cvent (2020), great hospitality managers care about how much their customers enjoy their experience and are always looking for new ways to improve every aspect of a visit.

Overseeing the day-to-day administrative, operational and commercial tasks of businesses such as hotels, resorts, restaurants, catering facilities, shops, casinos, amusement parks and many other related businesses is actually what hospitality management consists of. The hospitality industry includes everything from large hotel chains to the smallest food service establishments. According to Revfine (2021), your goal as a manager in hospitality management is to make your guests feel at ease and to ensure they have the best possible experience at your establishment.

2. Hospitality Industry

The hospitality industry is widely regarded as a subset of the broader service industry, with an emphasis on leisure rather than more basic needs. According to Revfine (2019), the hospitality industry encompasses a wide range of businesses and services related to recreation and customer satisfaction. A distinguishing feature of the hospitality industry is that it focuses on concepts of luxury, pleasure, enjoyment, and experiences rather than necessities and essentials. The hospitality industry is divided into 3 sectors are below:

1. Accommodation

The hospitality industry is all about providing temporary accommodation for customers. It is most often associated with the tourism industry where people book a vacation or trip and need accommodation. However, the accommodation sector also caters to locals looking for a short break from everyday life or needing temporary housing for almost any other reason.

2. Food & Beverages

Most food and beverage services fall under the hospitality industry because they provide opportunities for people to spend their free time and disposable income, as well as socialize and enjoy experiences. Here too, the food and beverage industry serves a diverse clientele, including tourists, locals, expats and passers-by.

3. Travel & Tourism

The hospitality and tourism industries are inextricably linked. Many services that are classified as tourism products are also classified as hospitality products as they relate to leisure, customer satisfaction, enjoyment, experience and use of disposable income. Importantly, the intersection between tourism and hospitality is about the service rather than the final product.

4. Coffee Industry

Coffee by-products are abundant in carbs, proteins, pectin's, bioactive compounds including polyphenols, and are inexpensive renewable resources (Murthy and Madhava Naidu, 2010). Coffee is an important product, and the operations that follow it, such as production, processing, trade, shipping, and marketing, offer jobs and are a significant business worldwide.

3. Coffee Industry in Indonesia

The Indonesian population is changing, favoring coffee shops more and more in their daily lives. Coffee has become a component of a lifestyle rather than merely a drowsiness reducer. Indonesian coffee enthusiasts are being spoiled with a wide selection of modern coffee menu options. Coffee shops are widely dispersed, even sprouting in isolated locations, ranging in size from small, simple coffee shops to lavish, minimalist coffee shops that offer the highest quality of service. Particularly millennials who enjoy contemporary coffee, such as milk coffee, palm sugar milk coffee, and other varieties of coffee sachets with different brands.

Table 1. The Comparison of Price for One Variant in Starbucks and Some Local Coffee Shops in Medan

Name of Coffee Shop	Price of Americano
Starbucks	Rp. 38,000
MADDIN	Rp. 25,000
Moscot.co	Rp. 28,000
Warung by Tangga	Rp. 21,000
Coffeenatics	Rp. 30,000

(Sources: Accessed Through Grab App and Google Maps)

METHODOLOGY

1. Population and Sample

According to Sugiyono (2017:215), the population is an area for generalization made up of things or subjects with particular attributes and characteristics chosen by researchers to be researched before conclusions are produced. Along with people, objects and other natural elements also make up the population. In this study, the population will be used to determine whether price, product quality, and service quality have an impact on customers' decisions to make purchases. Additionally, customers will be asked to complete a questionnaire to collect numerical data that will be used in a test to demonstrate the relationship between the variables.

Sugiyono (2016) claims that the sample reflects the size and features of the population. Sugiyono (2017) claims that the sample is a subset of the population, the source of the data used in research, and that the population is made up of a variety of characteristics. To select the research sample for this study, the author will employ a non-probability sampling technique. According to Gay and Diehl (1992), the sample should be as big as it can be. According to Gay and Diehl (1992), the more samples that are collected, the more representative they will be and the more generalizable the conclusions will be. However, the nature of research will determine the acceptable sample size.

- The minimal sample size for descriptive research is 10% of the population.
- The minimum sample size for correlational research is 30 participants.
- The sample size for a causal comparative study is 30 participants per group.
- The minimal sample size for experimental study is 15 people per group.

RESULT

1. Validity Test

A questionnaire survey is the instrument of this research. To ensure that each variable statement, including the indicators, is valid for this study, researchers will perform a validity test to assess the quality of the study. Indicates whether the results of the study are exactly in line with the objectives. Then this is also show how well our results match the generally accepted theory. In the validity test, researchers use and output data from 30 out of the total number of survey respondents. Validity test is used to test each variable used in this study. The sample to be used for this instrument test is the first 30 respondents, in order to obtain a critical

point with a significant level of 5% ($r_{\alpha;n-2} = r_{0.025;28}$) of 0.361. If the value of r count $>$ r 2 table, then the statement item can be declared valid.

Tabel 2. Validity Test Results on Product Service Variable

Number	r count	r tabel	Information
1	0.654	0.361	Valid
2	0.644	0.361	Valid
3	0.700	0.361	Valid
4	0.652	0.361	Valid
5	0.722	0.361	Valid
6	0.392	0.361	Valid
7	0.529	0.361	Valid
8	0.768	0.361	Valid

In table 2 it is known that the correlation of all statement items in the product service variable has a value greater than r table. Therefore, it can be concluded that all statement items on these variables are declared valid.

Tabel 3. Validity Test Result on Service Quality Variable

Number	r count	r tabel	Information
1	0.853	0.361	Valid
2	0.656	0.361	Valid
3	0.777	0.361	Valid
4	0.754	0.361	Valid
5	0.832	0.361	Valid

In table 3 it is known that the correlation of all statement items on the service quality variable has a value greater than r table. Therefore, it can be concluded that all statement items on these variables are declared valid.

Tabel 4. Validity Test Result on Price Variable

Number	r count	r tabel	Information
1	0.767	0.361	Valid
2	0.827	0.361	Valid
3	0.658	0.361	Valid
4	0.730	0.361	Valid
5	0.725	0.361	Valid
6	0.643	0.361	Valid
7	0.806	0.361	Valid
8	0.819	0.361	Valid

In table 4 it is known that the correlation of all statement items on the variable price towards has a value greater than the r table. Therefore, it can be concluded that all statement items on these variables are declared valid.

Tabel 5. Validity Test Result on Purchase Decision Variabel

Number	r count	r tabel	Information
1	0.762	0.361	Valid
2	0.832	0.361	Valid
3	0.649	0.361	Valid
4	0.810	0.361	Valid
5	0.889	0.361	Valid

In table 5 it is known that the correlation of all statement items on the purchase decision variable has a value greater than r table. Therefore, it can be concluded that all statement items on these variables are declared valid.

2. Reliability Test

In addition to validity tests, reliability tests should also be performed to test the reliability and consistency of study data. The purpose of reliability testing is to demonstrate reliability by checking whether studies are conducted under identical conditions and are consistent and to what extent the results are reproducible. Reliability test is used to measure the consistency of constructs or research variables. An instrument is said to be reliable if it has a Cronbach's alpha value greater than 0.6 (Priyatno, 2013: 30).

Tabel 6. Instrument Reliability Test Results on Product Service, Service Quality, Price Towards, and Purchase Decision Variables

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Tipping Point	Information
Product Service	0.767	0.6	Reliabel
Service Quality	0.832	0.6	Reliabel
Price Towards	0.882	0.6	Reliabel
Purchase Decision	0.849	0.6	Reliabel

Table 6 shows that the Cronbach's alpha values for product service, service quality, price towards, and purchase decision variables are 0.767, 0.832, 0.882, and 0.849 respectively. Cronbach's alpha obtained has a value greater than 0.6, so it can be concluded that the instruments of all research variables are reliable.

3. Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics is a method used to describe, summarize, and analyze data numerically or graphically. The purpose of descriptive statistics is to provide a better understanding of the characteristics or patterns that exist in the data. The three groups of statistical measures that are often used in descriptive statistics are central tendency, dispersion measures, and data form.

Tabel 7. Results of Descriptive Statistics for Each Statement on Product Service Variable

	X1.1	X1.2	X1.3	X1.4	X1.5	X1.6	X1.7	X1.8
N	Valid	126	126	126	126	126	126	126
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean	4.37	4.51	4.38	4.43	4.35	4.13	4.20	4.39
Median	4.00	5.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
Mode	4	5	5	4	4	4	4	5
Std. Deviation	0.627	0.603	0.679	0.586	0.661	0.790	0.770	0.645
Variance	0.394	0.364	0.462	0.343	0.437	0.624	0.592	0.416

In table 7 it is known that the average value ranges from 4.13 to 4.51. This shows that the majority of respondents gave the answer "Agree" on each statement which is an indicator of the product service variable. Each statement has a median value of four, except for the second statement. The answer most often chosen by respondents is "Agree". This can be seen from the median and mode values, where there are five statements that have a mode value of 4. The fourth statement on this variable has the lowest variance value, meaning that in this statement there are many respondents who choose the answer "Agree".

Tabel 8. Results of Descriptive Statistics for Each Statement on Service Quality

		Variable				
		X2.1	X2.2	X2.3	X2.4	X2.5
Valid	126	126	126	126	126	
Missing	0	0	0	0	0	
Mean		4.29	4.29	4.32	4.34	4.25
Median		4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
Mode		4	4	4	5	5
Std. Deviation		0.668	0.591	0.723	0.671	0.769
Variance		0.446	0.350	0.522	0.451	0.591

In table 8 it is known that the average value ranges from 4.25 to 4.34. This shows that the majority of respondents gave the answer "Agree" on each statement which is an indicator of service quality variables. Each statement has a median value of four. The answer most often chosen by respondents is "Agree". This can be seen from the median and mode values, where there are three statements that have a mode value of 4. The second statement on this variable has the lowest variance value, meaning that in this statement there are many respondents who choose the answer "Agree".

Tabel 9. Results of Descriptive Statistics for Each Statement on Price

		Variable							
		X3.1	X3.2	X3.3	X3.4	X3.5	X3.6	X3.7	X3.8
N	Valid	126	126	126	126	126	126	126	126
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		4.16	4.24	4.33	4.33	4.29	4.13	3.80	4.04
Median		4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
Mode		4	4	5	4	4	4	4	4
Std. Deviation		0.753	0.662	0.693	0.630	0.682	0.773	1.004	0.753
Variance		0.567	0.439	0.480	0.397	0.465	0.598	1.008	0.566

In table 9 it is known that the average value ranges from 3.80 to 4.33. This shows that the majority of respondents gave the answer "Agree" in each statement which is an indicator of the price towards variable. Each statement has a median value of four. The answer most often chosen by respondents is "Agree". This can be seen from the median and mode values, where there are seven statements that have a mode value of 4. The fourth statement on this variable has the lowest variance value, meaning that in this statement there are many respondents who choose the answer "Agree".

Tabel 10. Results of Descriptive Statistics for Each Statement on Purchase

	Decision Variable					
	Y.2	Y.3	Y.4	Y.5	Y.6	
N	Valid	126	126	126	126	126
	Missing	0	0	0	0	0
Mean		4.15	4.30	4.32	4.15	4.17
Median		4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00
Mode		4	4	4	4	4
Std. Deviation		0.780	0.707	0.712	0.749	0.777
Variance		0.609	0.500	0.506	0.561	0.604

In table 10 it is known that the average value ranges from 4.15 to 4.32. This shows that the majority of respondents gave the answer "Agree" on each statement which is an indicator of the purchase decision variable. Each statement has a median value of four. The answer most often chosen by respondents is "Agree". This can be seen from the median and mode values, where all statements have a mode value of 4. The second statement on this variable has the lowest variance value, meaning that in this statement there are many respondents who choose the answer "Agree".

4. Classical Assumption Result Testing

1. Normality Test

The normality test aims to determine the distribution of data in a variable that will be used in a study whether the data is feasible or not for analysis. The normality test in this study used the Kolmogrov-Smirnov technique.

Tabel 11. Normality Test Results on Unstandardized Residual

		Residual
N		126
Normal Paramet ers	Mean	0.000
	Std. Deviation	1.903
Most Extreme Differe nces	Absolute	0.091
	Positive	0.062
	Negative	-0.091
Test Statistic		0.091
	Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.200

In table 11 it is known that Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) in the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test of the unstandardized residual variable resulting from the independent variable regression on the dependent variable yields a score of 0.200. The significance obtained has a value greater than the value of α (5%), so the decision obtained is to fail to reject H_0 . Therefore, it can be concluded that the data is normally distributed.

2. Linearity Test

The linearity test aims to determine whether the independent variable and the dependent variable have a linear relationship or not. The two variables are said to have a linear relationship if the significance value of the linearity is less than 0.05.

Tabel 12. Linearity Test Results of Each Independent Variable Against the Dependent Variable

Variable	Deviation from Linearity		Information
		Sig.	
Product Service		0.152	Linear
Service Quality		0.594	Linear
Price Towards		0.541	Linear

In table 12 it is known that the significance value of linearity for the product service variable is 0.152, the service quality variable is 0.594, and the price towards variable is 0.541. The significance resulting from these three variables has a value greater than 0.005, so that the decision to fail to reject H_0 is obtained. Therefore, the variables product service, service quality, and price towards each have a linear relationship with the purchase decision variable.

3. Multicollinearity Test

The multicollinearity test is used to determine whether there is multicollinearity by investigating the magnitude of the inter correlation between the independent variables. Whether there is multicollinearity can be seen from the magnitude of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). If the VIF value ≤ 10 , it can be stated that there is no multicollinearity.

Tabel 13. Multicollinearity Test Results on Product Service, Service Quality, and Price Variables

Variable	Tolerance	VIF	Information
Product Service	0.316	3.160	Multicollinearity Does Not Occur
Service Quality	0.322	3.104	Multicollinearity Does Not Occur
Price Towards	0.491	2.036	Multicollinearity Does Not Occur

In table 13 it is known that the VIF values obtained from the product service, service quality, and price towards variables are 3,160, 3,104, and 2,036 respectively. The VIF resulting from these three variables has a value less than 10. Thus, it can be concluded that in the regression model there is no multicollinearity in the independent variables.

4. Heteroscedasticity Test

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in the regression there is an inequality of variance from one residual observation to another. One of the statistical tests that can be used to detect the presence or absence of heteroscedasticity is the Glesjer test. If the resulting significance value is greater than 5%, then it can be stated that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity.

Tabel 14. Glejser Test Results on Regression Models of Independent Variables on Absolute Unstandardized Residual Values

Variable	Sig.	Information
Product Service	0.455	There is no Heteroscedasticity
Service Quality	0.688	There is no Heteroscedasticity
Price Towards	0.199	There is no Heteroscedasticity

In table 14 it is known that the significance values for the product service, service quality, and price towards variables respectively are 0.455, 0.688, and 0.199. The three significances have a value greater than 0.05, so that the decision to fail to reject H0 is obtained. Therefore, it can be concluded that there are no symptoms of heteroscedasticity in the regression model.

5. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

1. Regression Equation

Multiple linear regression analysis is a linear relationship between two or more independent variables with the dependent variable. This analysis is to determine the direction of the relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable which is positively or negatively related and to predict the value of the dependent variable if the independent variable increases or decreases. Multiple linear regression analysis is done by setting the equation.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \varepsilon$$

Tabel 15. Multiple Regression Model Results

Variable	Coefficient B
<i>Constant</i>	-0.953
Product Service	0.151
Service Quality	0.175
Price Towards	0.391

In table 15, the equation for the regression model in this study is obtained, namely: $Y^{\wedge} = -0.953 + 0.151X_1 + 0.175X_2 + 0.391X_3$

a. It is known that the constant value is -0.953. This means that if the product service, service quality, and price towards variables have no value or have a score of zero, then the purchase decision variable will have a score of -0.953 units.

b. It is known that the coefficient value of the product service variable is 0.151. This means that for every one increase in the score of the product service variable, the purchase decision variable will also increase by 0.151 assuming that the service quality and price towards variables are constant.

c. It is known that the coefficient value of the service quality variable is 0.175. This means that for every one increase in the score of the service quality variable, the purchase decision variable will also increase by 0.175 assuming the product service and price towards variables are constant.

d. It is known that the coefficient value of the price towards variable is 0.391. This means that for every one increase in the score of the price towards variable, the purchase decision variable will also increase by 0.391 assuming the product service and service quality variables are of constant value

6. T test

Basically, this is used to find out how much influence each independent variable (X) has on the dependent variable (Y). The t test is carried out by comparing the value of tcount with t table, with a significant level of 5%. If the value of t count > t table then H0 is rejected Ha is accepted, meaning that there is a significant influence between each independent variable and the dependent variable. If the value of t count <t table then Ho is accepted and Ha is rejected, meaning that there is no significant effect between each of the independent variables and the dependent variable.

Tabel 16. Regression Model Partial Test Results

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients			
	B	Std. Error	t	Sig.
1 (Constant)	-0.953	1.464	-0.651	0.516
X1	0.151	0.074	2.051	0.042
X2	0.175	0.101	1.736	0.085
X3	0.391	0.049	7.967	0.000

a. The Effect of Product Service Variable (X1) on Purchase Decision Variable (Y) From the analysis results obtained sig. the X1 variable is 0.042 <0.05 and the t count (2.051) > t table (1.979), then H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted. It can be concluded partially that there is a significant influence between product service and purchase decision.

b. The Effect of Service Quality Variable (X2) on Purchase Decision Variable (Y) From the analysis results obtained sig. the variable X2 is 0.085 > 0.05 and the value of t count (1.736) < t table (1.979), then H0 is accepted and Ha is rejected. It can be concluded that partially there is no significant effect between service quality on purchase decision

c. Effect of Price Towards Variable (X3) on Purchase Decision Variable (Y) From the analysis results obtained sig. the variable X3 is 0.000 <0.05 and the value of t count (7.967) > t table (1.979), then H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted. It can be concluded partially that there is a significant influence between price towards the purchase decision.

6. F Test

The f test is used to show whether all the independent variables in this regression model have a joint effect on the dependent variable.

Tabel 17. Results of the Regression Model Simultaneous

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	609.783	3	203.261	91.08	0.000
Residual	272.257	122	2.232	2	0
Total	882.040	125			

In table 17 it is known that the significant value for the influence of X1, X2, and X3 together on Y is 0.000. It is known that the calculated F value is 91,082 and the F table value is 2.68, so that the calculated F value > F table and a significant value of 0.000 < 0.05, then H0 is rejected and H3 is accepted. It can be concluded that the product service, service quality, and price towards variables together have a significant effect on the customer's purchase decision.

7. Coefficient of Determination

Coefficient of determination tests were performed to measure the model's ability to explain how the effects of the independent variables jointly (simultaneously) affect the dependent variable. This is indicated by the fitted R-squared value. The coefficient of determination is used to measure how far the model's ability to explain the variation in the dependent variable.

Tabel 18. Results of the Coefficient of Determination of the Regression Model

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.831	0.691	0.684	1.494

Table 18 shows that the R Square value is 0.691 or 69.1%. This means that 69.1% of the variation in the customer purchase decision variable can be explained by the product service, service quality, and price towards variables, while the remaining 30.9% is explained by other factors outside the research model. The results of the test for the coefficient of determination mean that there are still other independent variables that influence the customer's purchase decision at Starbucks Coffee in Diponegoro, Medan.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Conclusion

This section is to summarize the research findings and provide suggestions for readers and other researchers who may conduct future studies on product quality, service quality, price, and purchasing decisions. This is the conclusion of the research conducted and the data collected as follows:

1. The effect of service quality has a significant positive effect on Starbucks Coffee customer purchase decision at Diponegoro Medan, meaning that the better the service, the higher the level of satisfaction obtained by consumers. This is reasonable because consumers always see the most important in terms of service quality.

2. The effect of product quality has a significant positive effect on Starbucks Coffee customer purchase decision in Diponegoro, Medan meaning that the better the product quality, the higher the level of satisfaction created and obtained by consumers. This is reasonable because consumers feel their desires are fulfilled in product quality.

3. The effect of price has a positive but not significant effect on Starbucks Coffee customer purchase decision in Diponegoro, Medan meaning that consumers are indeed satisfied with the quality of service and product quality created, but consumers do not see much from the Starbucks price perspective. Consumers see more in terms of services and products provided.

4. The effect of service quality, product quality and price have a significant positive influence on Starbucks customer purchase decision in Diponegoro, Medan meaning that the better the service quality, product quality and price, the higher the level of satisfaction obtained by consumers. This is reasonable because it plays an important role in creating customer satisfaction.

Recommendation

Based on the conclusions described above, it shows that service quality, product quality and price have a very strong influence on consumer purchasing decisions at Starbucks Diponegoro, Medan. Here, the researchers put forward some suggestions for Starbucks Diponegoro, Medan in the future, namely as follows:

1. In terms of service quality, Starbucks Diponegoro, Medan should maintain its service by means of better speed of service, better excellent service, providing new or more facilities such as updated or faster wifi, lots of stop contacts or charges, and providing a more comfortable atmosphere so that consumers feel satisfied and prioritized in terms of service at Starbucks.

2. In terms of product quality, Starbucks Diponegoro, Medan should create new products for consumers, create unique product flavors, create better product quality, create coffee that is distinctive and much loved by the people of Indonesia. Where product quality must be maintained by maintaining product quality so that it reaches consumers in good condition.

3. In terms of price, Starbucks Diponegoro, Medan should create a premium brand, make Starbucks a consumer accessory, create brand loyalty and create a brand position. Starbucks Diponegoro should pay more attention to and improve the company's brand image. This can also be done by increasing the speed, accuracy, convenience and completeness provided so that consumers judge Starbucks Grand Indonesia as a reliable coffee store.

4. In terms of consumer purchasing decisions, Starbucks Diponegoro, Medan should continue to maintain the level of consumer purchasing decisions by continuing to provide satisfying service and provide value and benefits that exceed consumer expectations, so that consumers feel that everything is fulfilled at Starbucks Diponegoro, Medan.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic The Influence of Product Quality, Service Quality, and Price Towards Customer Purchase Decision at Starbucks Coffee in order to perfect this research and increase the reader's insight.

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